

بناء القدرات المحلية
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View from the Zahir al-Umar fort

Climate Vulnerability Assessment (CVA) Risks and Resilience in Shefa-'Amr

Key take-aways and recommendations

About

This research is part of the project “Harnessing expertise and local knowledge for the development of climate resilience in the city of Shefa-‘Amr”, led by The Galilee Society in partnership with the University of Haifa and the municipality of Shefa-‘Amr.

This document is a summary of the key take-aways and recommendations. For more details, see the full report on The [Galilee Society website](#).

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Opening remarks

We are proud to be the first Arab municipality in Israel to participate in a project focused on developing climate resilience in Shefa-'Amr: "Harnessing Professional Expertise and Localized Knowledge for Collaborative Climate Resilience in Shefa-'Amr".

This project is based, among other elements, on building sustainable channels, processes, and mechanisms that enable community involvement and empowerment across the city's diverse population, as well as strengthening collaboration between the city's political and professional leadership to establish policies and develop initiatives to build climate resilience in Shefa-'Amr.

This report is an important milestone and the result of professional, research-based, and collaborative work, which will serve us as we continue with this project. Its success will set an example for other localities, and also provide valuable insights for academic research in this field.

We extend our gratitude to our project partners, The Galilee Society for leading and managing the project, the University of Haifa for providing the academic framework and conducting a participatory vulnerability assessment, and the European Union and the MISEREOR Foundation for their funding and support. Above all, we thank the residents of Shefa-'Amr, the local organizations, and the department heads within the municipality for their cooperation, contributions, and dedication to the success of this project.

Developing climate resilience in Shefa-'Amr will continue to be a key part of the municipality's policy and strategic vision.

Nahed Khazem

Mayor

Omar Malek

Municipality CEO

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Executive summary

Background

The Mediterranean region is a climate hotspot. Temperatures are rising and many areas in Israel are predicted to have up to twice as many days above 34°C within the next decades. The region is getting drier. In Israel the annual rain volume is forecast to decrease. However, for the Galilee region specifically, annual rain volumes are predicted to increase slightly in the next couple of decades, before they decrease. More extreme climate events are expected, including heatwaves, droughts or more intense rain events. In this context, communities need to assess their vulnerability, adapt to the changes, and be ready to face climate-related risks. This is called '**climate change adaptation**'. In Israel, many cities have started working on Climate Adaptation Plans and implementation. Shefa-'Amr was the first Arab local authority in Israel to start working on climate resilience.

Objective

The objective of this research is to assess the socio-economic, health and wellbeing vulnerability to climate change in Shefa-'Amr, in order to identify risks and opportunities and define priorities for the Climate Adaptation Plan. The results and the participatory, mixed methods approach will also serve as a case study to guide other Arab localities in Israel. This is part of the project "Harnessing expertise and local knowledge for the development of climate resilience in the city of Shefa-'Amr", led by The Galilee Society in partnership with the University of Haifa and the municipality of Shefa-'Amr.

Participatory, mixed methods

Methods used: resident's survey (482 respondents), stakeholder interviews (37 stakeholders), focus groups including vulnerable groups (88 participants), documents and online media analysis, consolidation of quantitative and spatial datasets (climatic, socio-economic, land use/land cover, geographic), feedback group sessions (54 participants). The assessment used the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate change (UN IPCC) climate risk framework, which considers climate hazards, exposure and vulnerability.

Accessing up-to-date socio-economic data was a challenge, especially as the data from the 2022 national census is not available yet. Some gaps in government-provided data affect Arab localities specifically. In other cases, government-provided data is not completely reliable. The use of participatory and mixed methods partially helped address some of these gaps. Participatory methods also help raise awareness of risks and build ownership regarding preparedness planning.

Findings

- 1. Shefa Amr is already experiencing extreme heat and intense rainfall, with negative health and economic impacts.** For example, more than 50% of respondents in the residents' survey indicated that they have experienced 'some' or 'severe' negative health impacts from severe heat. The rainfall-related events map shows that there are floods almost every year, causing private and public financial damage.

This means that adaptation is not only required for future preparedness, but also to improve quality of life in the short-term.

- 2. Heat-related risks are relevant for the entire city, with several groups at higher risk.** Most of the city is exposed to heat stress in the summer, except for the forest. This forest will decrease

significantly due to the construction of a new neighborhood. People with higher exposure include outdoor workers; pedestrians; public sports field users (all unshaded). Heat-related sensitivity factors higher than nationally include diabetes (40% higher) and children with overweight (future cardiovascular risk). The percentage of people above age 65 is lower than nationally, but increasing. Shefa-‘Amr is in a low socioeconomic index cluster (3 out of 10). This impacts people’s ability to cope with heat-related risks, as well as other risks such as floods. People cope with the heat in various ways, but air conditioning has become the most significant one. This large dependence has financial and environmental costs, and is a risk in case of electricity cuts.

3. **Floods are not frequent, but do recur virtually every year, causing financial damage and frustration from the way they are handled by the municipality.** Records gathered from online media mostly show street flooding along the main wadi streams, as well as flooded private and public buildings, and also flooding in places that are not near a wadi. There is a lack of awareness as well as a lack of institutional and financial capacity to implement sustainable stormwater management practices.
4. **Climate change is a ‘threat multiplier’, as hazards exacerbate several existing issues.** For example, in Shefa-‘Amr as in many Arab localities in Israel, the existing lack of walkability, public spaces (especially within walking distance and serving different ages and genders), public safety and cleanliness reduce the ability to be active and social outdoors. Rising heat may further reduce this ability.

For the Climate Adaptation Plan to be most effective, it should be directly connected to other strategic plans that address these and other existing issues.

5. **There are limitations to the municipality’s institutional and financial capacity to address risks alone – some are more structural, others are more operational.** The centralized government limits the local authority’s capacity in some fields such as urban planning or public transport. Some risks require collaboration, sometimes based on goodwill, with authorities such as the Kishon Drainage Authority (flood risk), the Water and Sewage Corporation (sewage overflow risk) or the Jewish National Fund (forest fire risk).

The Climate Adaptation Plan should assess what can be implemented independently within the municipality’s authority and financial scope, and which measures require financial, policy or other support from/coordination with external stakeholders.

6. **Shefa-‘Amr has many resources that it can build on and strengthen for climate resilience.** There is an active civil society and a significant community willingness to take action (although this may be hindered by a low awareness of the concept of adaptation to climate change, and mistrust of the municipality). There are numerous health, social, educational and religious institutions that can contribute to climate resilience. Furthermore, while private land often complicates planning processes, with private building people have a personal interest in building climate-adapted homes. In addition, many climate adaptation measures connect with local traditions and heritage.

The Climate Adaptation Plan should plan for emergency response to events such as acute heat-related health events, floods, and forest fires. It should also plan broader urban and social measures to decrease (chronic) exposure and/or sensitivity, and increase adaptive capacity and climate resilience. It should focus on improving quality of life in existing neighborhoods, and on vulnerable groups.

This document is a summary of the key take-aways and recommendations. For more details, see the full report on The [Galilee Society website](#).

Background

- Globally and locally, the climate has already started to change. The Mediterranean region is particularly exposed to climate change. For example, **the average temperature in Israel is already 1.4°C higher than in 1950**. Climate change is expected to continue, as globally countries are not meeting their greenhouse gas emission reduction targets.
- In this context, countries, cities and people need to adapt to the changes, and be ready to face climate-related risks. This is called '**climate change preparedness**' or '**adaptation**'.
- In Israel, several cities have started working on Climate Adaptation Plans and implementation. Shefa-'Amr was the first Arab local authority in Israel to start working on climate resilience.

Objective

- The objective of this research is to assess the socio-economic, health and wellbeing vulnerability to climate change in Shefa-'Amr, in order to identify risks and opportunities and define priorities for the Climate Adaptation Plan.
- This will also serve as a case study to guide other Arab localities in Israel, as part of the project "Harnessing expertise and local knowledge for the development of climate resilience in the city of Shefa-'Amr" ('Climate Resilience' project), led by The Galilee Society in partnership with the University of Haifa and the municipality of Shefa-'Amr.

Study area: Shefa-'Amr urban municipality

- **Location:** Lower Galilee, about 20 km from the cities of Haifa, Nazareth and Acre
- **Climate:** Mediterranean climate characterized by 'hot, dry' summers. Over 600 mm of precipitation annually (September to May, with 70% between December and February)
- **Topography:** Shefa-'Amr is said to be built upon 7 hills. The hill slopes range from 10-20%. Average elevation is 137 meters, minimum 35 meters, maximum 310 meters. 4 seasonal wadi streams cross the municipal jurisdiction from (south)east to (north)west.
- **Land cover/land use:** 42.6% built-up (including 33.6% residential), 28.6% agricultural, 11.3% forest/woods, 17.6% other open space. Most of the jurisdiction and the built-up area are north of highway 79. Cultivated land and a few neighborhoods are to its south.
- **Population:** 43,023 inhabitants, including Muslim, Christian, Druze and Bedouin communities. The master outline plan is designed for 96,400 inhabitants. If the population continues to grow at the same pace as during the past decade, there will be about 63,000 inhabitants by 2050.
- **CBS socio-economic index:** cluster 3 out of 10 (10 is the highest), similar to many other Arab localities in Israel.¹

¹ CBS is the Central Bureau of Statistics. The socio-economic index uses multiple demographic, educational, employment, income and standard of living variables. In 2019, cluster 3 was the cluster with the highest number of Arab localities, 38% altogether, including Nazareth, as well as Tayibe and Tamra which are both of a similar size to Shefa-'Amr.

Morning heat stress index

Summer months, 10-11AM

The heat stress index combines surface temperature and air humidity.

Source: Shafran-Nathan and Broday, in preparation

“In summer I sleep all the time because **I’m tired all the time.**”

In this heat, it’s unbearable, because I have headaches and low blood pressure, and **it really bothers me**, the heat.”

“Without the A/C we can’t cope. The A/C is on all the time, **and this has a cost.**”

“We have been coping with the heat for a **long time** already.”

Quotes from Shefa-’Amr residents in focus group discussions

Total number of days in the year with temperature above 34°C

Coping with heat in Shefa-'Amr – existing examples

Air conditioning

Shading at (new) playgrounds

Heat-adapted design

Summer activities

“Sabeel” fountain in shaded spot to rest

Shading by local business

Adaptation measures for increase in temperature and in number of hot days - examples

Solar shade cover
(Kfar Saba – Sorkis school)
++ Financial benefits

Shade with local design
(Jerusalem, The Urban Clinic)
++ Tourism and heritage

Cooling appliances upgrade, energy efficiency
++ Lowering electricity bill and heat/greenhouse gas emissions

Heat waves/ power outages planning
++ Overall emergency preparedness

Streetside trees (New York, Spain – examples of narrow streets with parking)
++ Cleaner air, mental health

Development of open public spaces as community projects
(Acre 5000)
++ Social capital

Fig. 1 - Shefa-'Amr 10 statistical areas and 52 neighborhoods

GIS mapping: Guy Steenkamp and Alix Pahaut. Neighborhoods and statistical areas according to GOVMAP, with a few modifications based on local input.

- **10 statistical areas:** These are not administrative units. They are defined by the CBS and also used by some other organizations (e.g. Ministry of Welfare) for population statistics. The aim is for statistical areas to be “as homogeneous as possible, with borders determined according to various criteria such as land use, main period of construction, and engineering and demographic considerations” (CBS 2022). Note that in the 2022 Census (data not available yet), the CBS also used ‘sub-quarters’ as units, and Shefa-'Amr was divided into 3 sub-quarters.
- **52 neighborhoods:** These are not administrative units, nor official. There may be some disagreements on the borders and naming of neighborhoods. Within the above map from the national Geospatial Portal ‘Govmap’, a few names have been modified to represent names more recognizable to the community, based on interviews.
- **20 planning areas (not included here):** Shefa-'Amr’s department of engineering has divided the city differently, into 20 different ‘**planning areas**’. These planning areas do relate to existing neighborhoods, but some are grouped, and the borders are not exactly the same as in the Govmap view.

Research methods

This climate risk/vulnerability assessment used six research methods:

1. Online residents survey: August – October 2021, 482 respondents
2. Focus groups with community members and municipality professionals 2022 – 2023: 88 participants in 14 groups²
3. Key informant interviews 2021 – 2023: interviews with 37 key informants

4. Consolidation of quantitative and spatial datasets (climatic, socio-economic, land use/land cover, geographic), which amounted to 47 indicators
5. Documents and online media analysis, incl. online media records of rainfall-related events
6. Feedback sessions with community members and municipality professionals regarding research results, in 2 phases (2022 – 2023): 54 participants in 8 groups²

This assessment uses the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (UN IPCC)'s climate risk framework. In this framework, climate risk is a combination of the climate hazards, exposure and vulnerability.

Fig. 2 – Climate risk framework

Note on data and methods

Accessing relevant and up-to-date data was a challenge. Several gaps in government-provided data affect Arab localities specifically:

1. Outdated socio-economic index per statistical area (except for Nazareth and Rahat)
2. Lack of welfare data per statistical area (except for Nazareth and Rahat)
3. Mapping of streetside tree canopy is missing for several Arab localities (but is available for Shefa-'Amr).

In the first 2 cases, the data from the 2022 population census is expected to address several gaps. However, it has not yet been published.

In other cases, government-provided data is not always completely reliable. For example, flood risk mapping in the Ministry of the Environment's new climate risk mapping does not fully match with our data from the field. Furthermore, the possible lack of accuracy is not always communicated clearly together with the data. For example, access to medical services indicators from the Ministry of Health have important caveats that are not displayed with the data. Sometimes, different sources of data contradict each other, such as regarding the percentage of agricultural land in the locality. Considering this, the use of participatory and mixed methods was useful to help address such data issues. Interviewees and focus group participants provided data, as well as provided feedback on the findings. Also important, participatory methods also help raise awareness of climate-related risks and build ownership regarding preparedness planning.

² Focus groups and feedback session groups included older women, older men, people who work outdoors, people involved in agriculture, young adults, civil society volunteers, and municipality employees. Throughout these groups the different sub-communities were represented (Muslim, Christian, Druze, Bedouin).

Examples of impacts of intense rain events

December 23, 2023
 Examples of rainfall-related events
 Only events for which a photo was available
 and approximate location is known
 Larger circle: specific location not known

Examples of impacts shown in photos:

- Flooded store, more than 70 cm
- Flooded street, car stuck
- Flooded street
- Flooded house
- Flooded streets and yards
- Flooded house/ building
- Flooded street
- Flooded street
- Flooded street, flooded private gardens
- Flooded street/yard, more than 70 cm
- Flooded public building and yard
- Flooded vegetable store
- Flood street, more than 70 cm, car stuck
- Flooded yard
- Flooded yard, more than 70 cm

Impacts and costs

- **Damage to private and public property** (streets, yards buildings, cars, furniture, stored goods, etc.)
- **First response costs** (rescue services, pumps, cranes, etc.)
- **Injuries resulting from accidents** (e.g. from potholes)
- **Pollution from sewage** overflow
- **Repair costs** (potholes, infrastructure)
- **Traffic delays, disrupted services** (e.g. school)
- **Lawsuits**
- **Residents' dissatisfaction and loss of trust**

Preparedness and coping: existing examples

New drainage pipe in Al-Birke neighborhood, Sept 2022

Cleaning channel drains before winter, Oct 2021

Pumping truck used in Wadi Al-Saqia, Jan 2021

Additional tools for urban runoff management: examples

Runoff retention (infiltration, recharge)

Permeable roundabouts, Agma ++ Allows for trees and plants

Grass pavers ++ Lower temperature than asphalt

Permeable/draining pavement (Agma)

Runoff detention and retention

Regulation basin included in TAMAL 1036 upstream of the Hanaton/Al-Karak wadi - 1 out 4 in the Shefa-'Amr Drainage Master Plan

"Al Zohour Green Triangle", Amman. Among other goals, the project aims to contain flash flood waters by collecting them in underground tanks, and then releasing them for later use.

Runoff conduction

Permeable traffic calming elements, e.g. curb extensions or traffic islands ++ Road safety, allows for trees and plants

Permeable traffic island. Infiltration channel prior to planting of greenery, Gil'ad street in Pardes Hanna

Local climate hazards

- **Hotter:** According to climate forecasts, the temperatures in the region are expected to continue to increase if greenhouse gas emissions continue to increase. **Within the next few decades, many areas in Israel including in the north are predicted to experience up to twice as many days above 34°C** compared to the past few decades.
- **Drier:** Whether greenhouse gas emissions continue to increase or stabilize, the annual volume of precipitation is forecasted to decrease in Israel.³ An increase in frequency and/or intensity of drought is forecasted as well.
- **More extreme rain events:** A small increase of days with intense rainfall is forecasted, together with a decrease in total number of rainy days.

Fig. 3 – **Heat stress, Shefa-'Amr (summer morning)**

This index measures a combination of land surface temperature and humidity

The index developed by researchers from the Technion is an average from May to September of each year. Land surface temperature satellite data is from 10-11AM.

Source: Shafran-Nathan, R., Broday, D. M. Long-term changes in meteorological conditions and their effects on exposure to excessive heat. In preparation.

³ A decrease in total rainfall volume is forecasted in the Galilee and in the rest of the country by 2100. However, in the Galilee, a small rainfall volume increase of 1.2-2.5% is forecasted between 2021-2050, compared to 1988-2017.

Local climate future risks and existing impacts

The local climate hazards may lead to a variety of **health, wellbeing, social and economic risks**, as illustrated by Figure 4:

Fig. 4 - Risks for Shefa-‘Amr based on expected local climate change phenomena

¹ Mosquitoes – viruses like West Nile Virus, sandfly – leishmaniasis

- **Extreme heat is not a new hazard** since Shefa-‘Amr’s has always had a Mediterranean climate characterized by hot, dry summers, and residents have developed various common coping methods.
- Based on the residents’ perceptions as reported from the survey and the focus groups, **extreme heat is perceived as a health, wellbeing and economic burden by a large part of the population.**
 - For example, more than 50% of the survey respondents indicated that they had “some” or “serious” health consequences from extreme heat (56% of female respondents, and 41% of male respondents).
- There are some known heat-related health risks that may exist in Shefa-‘Amr even if residents are not aware of them, because they are not **easily identifiable.**
 - For example, beyond immediate risks such as heat stroke, studies have found associations between heat and the risks of cardiovascular, pulmonary and suicide events, as well as kidney damage and increases in domestic and street violence (see ‘physical sensitivity to heat-related health risks’).
- **Rainy days were described both as a blessing and as a source of damage.**
- Floods are frequent in the winter. Most of them incur relatively modest damage, with some exceptions. Floods seem to be a source of **frustration from the way they are managed by the municipality** because of their ongoing recurrence, especially in areas of high exposure.
- These impacts may become more serious as **climate change intensifies**, especially if Shefa-‘Amr’s exposure and vulnerability are not reduced.

Quotes 1 - Impacts of heat and rain, focus group participants

Focus group participants – impacts of heat

“In the summer season, I sleep all the time, because **I’m tired all the time.**”

“In such high heat, I can’t stand it, because I have headaches, and I have low blood pressure, and **it really bothers me, the heat.**”

“Without air conditioning we can’t handle it. The whole time the air conditioning is on **and it has a cost.**”

“We have been dealing with the heat for **many years.**”

Focus group participants – impacts of rain

“I have a friend, **several times the water flooded his house** [and the furniture was damaged], he got rid of it and bought new furniture. And they have a disabled family member. The municipality comes, the water corporation too, they look, but this doesn’t really help, it’s like giving paracetamol to a sick person.”

“[When it rains in an area that is littered with garbage] instead of a refreshing feeling, it gives a **bad feeling.** There should be a good smell with rain, instead it’s disgusting.”

“During this season [March 2022], whoever grew beans and spinach, **the rain hurt the crops.** Too much cold hurts agriculture, and no rain at all is not good either.”

Playground in Al-Fawar neighborhood

View from the main community center

Climate hazards and risks: recommendations

Based on the expected climate trends, **municipality departments and other organizations** (schools, healthcare facilities, social services, local businesses, etc.) should map out which of the identified climate-related risks are relevant to their specific areas of responsibility.

For example, the risk of fire damage and need for evacuation due to a forest fire is mostly relevant to the schools and community center in the areas at the edge of the forest. However, the risk of exposure to smoke from a forest fire is also relevant to the rest of the city. As another example, a prolonged electricity cut on a hot day has **different risks for specific contexts**: decrease in students’ ability to concentrate in school, health risk to nursing home residents, inability to cool heat-sensitive goods for businesses (e.g. medications, meat), etc.

Exposure

“**Exposure**” assesses how the natural and built environment exposes people more or less to climate hazards – for example, people in areas with many trees may be less exposed to heat.

Exposure to heat

- **The heat stress index** developed by researchers at the Technion measures a combination of heat (land surface temperature) and humidity for the summer period, around 10AM – see Figure 4. **Heat stress has clearly increased** in Shefa-‘Amr over the past 4 decades. The two likely drivers of this increase are climate change (increase in temperature), and land use changes (increase in built-up area).
- Outdoors, areas with more trees and vegetation cover clearly show lower heat stress. Both in the morning and the evening, the coolest part within the municipal jurisdiction is the eastern Shefa-‘Amr forest.
- In the summer, Shefa-‘Amr’s built-up area is less hot than the open spaces on the outskirts of the city in the morning, and vice versa in the evening. This may be because most of the outskirts are agricultural fields, which are bare and dry in the summer. Bare, dry soil warms up fast in the morning, but in the evening, they cool down faster than building materials like concrete and **asphalt that retain heat for a longer time.**
- Indoors, people depend primarily on active cooling via **air conditioning**. Certain common design features provide passive cooling, but possibly less than in traditional architecture. No buildings have ‘green building’ certification yet.

Trees

- **The tree canopy coverage for Shefa-‘Amr’s built-up area is estimated to be 4%**, which is the same as the average for localities in Israel. However, many of these are private olive tree grove plots, many of which may become residential space in the future.
- For the majority of streets in Shefa-‘Amr, the **street tree canopy coverage is estimated to be 0-5%**. Nationally, 54% of streets are estimated to have a coverage of 5-20%. The national target for streets with pedestrian passage (streets with public transport, commercial activities, etc.) is 70% street tree canopy coverage by 2040.
- The Old City neighborhoods, the area around the municipality, and the industrial area have the fewest trees. On the other hand, in the Old City neighborhoods there are more narrow streets with dense building, providing shade from the buildings.
- Without a strategic plan for tree preservation and planting, **the urban tree cover will decrease** due to tree cutting for expected residential buildings and the development of new neighborhoods.
 - In the past 4 years, 8,217 trees received licenses for felling or moving. Most of these were pine, olive and cypress trees for the development of infrastructure and residential building. 7,500 of these are for the new neighborhood in the east of the city according to the employment and residential complexes development plan “Tamal/1036”.

Morning heat stress index

Summer months, 10-11AM

A – Forest, football fields (synthetic grass), community center, school

B – Municipality and surroundings

C – Released Soldiers new neighborhood “A”

D – Alkharoubiye neighborhood

The heat stress index combines land surface temperature and humidity

Source: Shafran-Nathan, R., Broday, D. M (in preparation)

- Outdoors, areas with **more trees and vegetation cover** clearly show lower heat stress. Both in the morning and the evening, the coolest part within the municipal jurisdiction is the eastern Shefa-Amr forest.
- In the summer, Shefa-Amr’s built-up area is less hot than the open spaces on the outskirts of the city in the morning, and vice versa in the evening. This may be because most of the outskirts are agricultural fields, which are bare and dry in the summer. Bare, dry soil warms up fast in the morning, but in the evening, they cool down faster than building **materials like concrete and asphalt that retain heat for a longer time.**

Evening temperature difference between the urban built-up area and its surrounding open spaces

August, 9PM

Legend:

Urban heat island map: temperature in August at 21:00, comparison between the built-up localities and their open surroundings (10 km)

National climate risks map (initial version)

Source: The Ministry of Environmental Protection

Fig. 5 – Roadside tree canopy cover index

Legend: percentage of roadside tree canopy cover

51%-100% ■ 26%-50% ■ 16%-25% ■ 6%-15% ■ 0%-5% ■ 0% ■

Source: [National mapping \(details\)](#)

Shade in public outdoor facilities

- There is a lack of shade in public outdoor facilities, except for playgrounds which are all shaded (except for one which is being renovated).
 - **None of the sports fields are shaded.** Many of them are covered in synthetic turf, and these show a much higher summer morning heat index than other areas.
 - **Many sidewalks and bus stops are not shaded.**

Populations with high exposure to heat

Shefa-‘Amr residents who are particularly exposed to heat include:

- **People who work outdoors:** 16.5% of Shefa-‘Amr male residents who worked in 2008, worked in construction and civil engineering, which often includes outdoor work. In statistical area 1, this is the case for 29.9%.
- **Children** who walk to school or play in non-shaded sports fields.
- **Pedestrians in general**, including those walking to bus stops.

Exposure to heat: recommendations

- The municipality should perform a **shade mapping** for critical community outdoor spaces such as bus stops, schools, sidewalks, etc.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include a strategic shading plan, including tree planting and preservation as well as artificial shade and maintenance. This plan should involve public institutions, private organizations, and the community.
- **Trees that provide significant shade should be promoted**, together with other factors such as low irrigation requirements and contributions to local biodiversity and heritage.
- Covering sports fields with **solar shade structures** can provide triple benefit of shade, protection from rain, and solar energy.
- The municipality must include shading in every public space development project, including in submissions to request for government funding (**calls for proposal**). Every such development plan should include shading of elements like sidewalks, streets, sports facilities and schoolyards, and public building development plans should meet standard requirements for green construction including passive cooling.
- Efforts to increase adaptive capacity should include a **focus on people who work outdoors**.

Exposure to risk of forest fire

- There were **24 cases of forest fires** in the Eastern Shefa-'Amr forest in the previous decade, most of them small, except for one fire in May 2019 that burned 266 dunams. This forest is managed by Keren Kayemeth Lelsrael-Jewish National Fund (KKL-JNF).
- The areas at the interface of the Eastern Shefa-'Amr forest and Abu Shehab, Al-Karak, and the main community center require **fire buffer zones** according to an assessment by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.

Fig. 6 – Eastern Shefa-'Amr forest: forest fires January 2013 - January 2023

Source: KKL-JNF GIS site

Exposure to risk of forest fires: recommendations

- The **fire buffer zones** should be implemented, and KKL-JNF should place signs alerting visitors regarding the prevention of forest fires.
- An **updated evaluation** of the need for fire buffer zones should be performed, taking the TAMAL 1036 plan into account.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include an **emergency plan** in case of forest fire including coordination with stakeholders (KKL-JNF, fire department, police, Home Front Command, emergency health services, schools, community center and other institutions adjacent to the forest, emergencies volunteer group, etc.), equipment, and communication with the community.

Exposure to rainfall-related events

- Up until 2024, there was **no flood risk map for Shefa-‘Amr based on a hydrodynamic model**. To compensate for this, flood risk was assessed in a broader, macro-level way by considering existing data on streams, drainage and **past rainfall-related events**.
- **Fluvial flooding**: the main exposure to floods in Shefa-‘Amr is along wadi streams that flow through the current built-up area. The streams are Wadi Al-Saqia (Nahal Shefaram), and Wadi Al-Karak and Wadi Abu Afen (Nahal Hanaton), including their confluence point in the Al-Ayn neighborhood from where they flow out further to the Western entrance of the city (Nahal Shefaram).
 - Currently there is no major exposure associated with Wadi Al-Fawar (Nahal Shafron) due to a low density of buildings. However, there are **future residential neighborhoods** planned at some locations along this wadi.
 - Along the wadis, the main risk is flooding in the street. However, there are also cases of flooding in basements and in stores.
- Apart from exposure to street floods and potholes along wadi streams, there are other exposure factors for two different rainfall-related issues in Shefa-‘Amr:
 - **Pluvial flooding**: rainwater sometimes creates a local flooded zone in areas that are not near a wadi stream, due to street topography, the built environment (e.g. a wall that blocks the flow of water, the entrance to a building that is lower than the street), or blocked drainage street gutters.
 - **Sewage overflow**: a mix of rainwater and sewage sometimes overflows into the street or into houses. Illegal connections of house rainwater gutters to the sanitary sewer system bring large volume of rainwater into the sanitary sewer system, which is not designed to receive rainwater in addition to sewage (a separate issue from blockages in the sewer system, which also cause some cases of overflow on dry days).
- In 2024 the Ministry of Environmental protection published a new national mapping of climate risks, including ‘urban local floods’ mapping.
 - For Shefa-‘Amr this mapping identifies exposure along the wadi streams, but **not in other areas**. This may be because of gaps in its model (e.g. it does not take land cover nor drainage infrastructure into account) – see figure 7.
 - In two cases the national mapping identifies wadi streams to be longer than what is shown in Govmap (‘Ayn ‘Afiye road/road 315 and Warat Jarus neighborhood), suggesting they may be **previously unrecognized risk areas**. Since the national climate risk mapping is new, the validity of insights at such a local, high-resolution level is not yet known.

Fig. 7 – Flood risk areas according to the national climate risks map (initial version)

Source: National climate risk map (initial version), Ministry of Environmental Protection

Examples of impacts of intensive rain which are not located close to a wadi stream: flooded house in Al-Kharubiye neighborhood 2021, road collapse in Al-Midan neighborhood 2018, flooded road in Bishop Hajar Road (close to the municipality) 2023

Tree canopy 2022

Source of the mapped data: National Tree Canopy Survey, 2023. Includes trees only in built-up areas (i.e. excludes most of Shefa-'Amr forest)

- **The tree canopy coverage for Shefa-'Amr's built-up area is estimated to be 4%**, which is the same as the average for localities in Israel. However, many of these are private olive tree grove plots, many of which may become residential space in the future.
- **For the majority of streets in Shefa-'Amr, the street tree canopy coverage is estimated to be 0-5%.** Nationally, 54% of streets are estimated to have a coverage of 5-20%.
- Without a strategic plan for tree preservation and planting, **the urban tree cover will decrease** due to tree felling for expected residential buildings and the development of new neighborhoods.

Benefits of trees in the urban space

Shade and cooling

Cleaner air

Stormwater management

Noise reduction

Licenses to fell or move trees

Year	# of trees	Including
2022	269	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 217 trees for the development of New Released Soldiers Neighborhood (51 olive, 130 pine, 36 cypress) - 72 olive trees for residential construction, for example in the neighborhoods of Jabata (15) and Alkharoubia (18) - 2 pines, dead/highly prone to collapse
2021	96	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 40 olive trees for residential construction, for example in the Abu Thabet neighborhood (9) - 37 olive trees for the construction of a parking lot for Sakhnin College - 15 trees for the construction of the Shefa-'Amr-road 781 intersection (10 chinaberry, 3 ficus, 1 cypress, 1 pomegranate) - 13 ficus trees related to damage or blocking of a sidewalk
2020	62	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 28 trees for residential construction, for example in the Abu Shehab neighborhood (10 olive trees) - 28 trees to pave a road in the New Released Soldiers Neighborhood (21 cypress, 7 pine) - 5 trees for construction/installation of a road junction (olive and acacia saligna) - 1 cypress due to a health hazard
2019	290	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 245 Jerusalem pine trees for a school in the Abu Shehab neighborhood - 45 degenerated and dangerous dry trees (pine, cypress)

Notes: (1) There may be additional licenses. (2) Does not include TML/1036 development plan. (3) These figures show licenses issued, not whether the felling or moving was actually carried out. Some licenses are conditional on obtaining a building permit or start of construction.

Source: [Meirim association](#), Ministry of Agriculture

A Residential and business areas development in the east of the city will result in the felling of 7,500 trees.

Source: TML/1036 plan, govmap

B Expected future tree felling: example from plan G/10567, Jabata neighborhood G

Source: govmap

- Tree(s) to preserve
- Trees(s) to remove
- Public parks and playgrounds
- Existing planted forest

Traffic calming

Biodiversity

Aesthetics and heritage

Mental and physical health

Exposure to rainfall-related events: recommendations

- In order to monitor trends over time, the municipality should keep a **record of rainfall-related events** such as floods (date, location, impact, measures taken, recommendations), and request similar data from the Water and Sewage Corporation regarding sewage overflow events.
- A **flood risk map based on a more complete hydrodynamic model** (see ‘adaptive capacity’) may help the municipality identify risk areas more accurately. This may require a mapping of the drainage infrastructure.
- Flood risk maps and forecasts should be easily accessible **and proactively communicated to the community** to avoid construction in flood risk areas and/or allow appropriate protective measures, including for future residential areas such as in Warat Jarus neighborhood and along Wadi Al-Fawar (Nahal Shafron).
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include measures to **prevent high-risk building** (including basements) in exposed areas. These can include raising awareness among residents, not delivering building permits in risk areas, and preventing building without permits.

Vulnerability – sensitivity and adaptive capacity

Vulnerability is the propensity to be adversely affected (or harmed) by a hazard. For example, an older adult and a child may be similarly exposed to heat because they are in the same environment, but they may each have different levels of vulnerability to this heat.

“Vulnerability” can be divided into two more concepts: “**Sensitivity**” considers susceptibility to damage, often related to personal factors, and “**Adaptability**” considers the personal and social ability to prepare for, cope with, and recover from a hazard’s impact.

Relative social vulnerability to heat index

- In order to assess social vulnerability to heat **between statistical areas**, an index was developed using social and demographic data: age, type of household, physical capacity, occupational exposure to heat, socio-economic index.
- **Based on 2008 figures, the two statistical areas with the highest social vulnerability to heat are statistical areas number 7 and number 1.**
 - For statistical area number 7 (Old City neighborhoods), this is driven more by **health-related heat sensitivity factors**. The area has a higher percentage of older adults, of older adults who live alone, and of people with limited physical ability to perform daily activities.
 - For statistical area number 1 (western neighborhoods), this is driven more by **economic factors**. The area has a relatively lower socio-economic index, and a higher percentage of people who work in construction (exposure to heat factor).
- The above are not the only two areas with social vulnerability – for example statistical area number 6 also has a high percentage of older adults, and statistical area 2 also has a relatively low socio-economic index.
- The index needs to be **updated** once the data from the 2022 census is available.

Fig. 8 – Relative social vulnerability to heat index, 2008

Index calculated using CBS data. Mapping performed using ArcGIS Pro.

Sensitivity to climate change

Health and heat

Physical and health-related sensitivity to heat – higher than national average

- **The prevalence of diabetes** in Shefa-‘Amr is 79.6 per 1,000. This is 40% higher than the national average. It has been increasing over the past years.
- **The prevalence of overweight or obesity** in grades 1 and 7 is 25% and 45% in Shefa-‘Amr. Both are higher than the national average, and have been increasing over the past years. This is a risk factor for future cardiovascular conditions.
- In the overall Arab population, the rate of **smoking among men** has had increases and decreases over the last two decades. In 2020 the rate was at its lowest, at 38.2%. This is 69% higher than the national average for men.

Fig. 9 – Sensitivity to heat: examples of factors that are higher than national average, trend increasing over time

Physical and health-related sensitivity to heat – lower than national average

- 7.3% of the population is **older than 65 years old**. This is lower than the national average (12.3%), but the percentage has been increasing steadily over the past years.
- 7.8% of the population is **younger than 5 years old**. This is lower than the national average (9.7%), and has been decreasing over the past years.
- In the overall Arab population, the rate of **smoking among women** has had increases and decreases over the last two decades. In 2020 the rate was at its highest, at 10.2%. This is 35% lower than the national average for women.

Shefa-'Amr-specific data is not available for other risk factors such as: kidney disease, depression, psychotic disorders, pregnant women (risk of premature birth and low birth weight), and recreational drug use.

Another risk factor is **older adults living alone**. In 2008 this rate was lower in Shefa-'Amr (29.8%) compared to the national population (35.2%), however the trend over time is not known.

Fig. 10 – Sensitivity to heat: examples of factors that are lower than national average, mixed trends over time

Economy - Economic sensitivity to heat and precipitation-related risks

- **Weather conditions impact agricultural yields and profit.**
 - Shefa-'Amr has an agricultural past, and today about 25% of the municipal territory is used for agriculture. However, due to multiple political, social and climatic processes, it is estimated that, today, fewer than 20 people in Shefa-'Amr depend on agricultural yield as their main source of income.
 - Olive groves make up more than half of the municipal territory used for agriculture. Income from olives is less sensitive to drought as the local rain-fed Syrian variety is relatively drought-resistant, and olives are usually a secondary source of income.
 - Grains and vegetables are more sensitive to drought as grains are rainfed and vegetables require increasing amounts of irrigation.
- **Weather conditions may impact number of working hours and productivity for outdoor jobs** such as construction and infrastructure.
- **(Extreme) heat may affect certain businesses**, for example shops that store fruits and vegetables outdoors. In the case of an extended electricity cut, businesses that require refrigeration may also be impacted.
- The municipality is economically sensitive to **damage related to extreme weather events**. Examples from floods in the previous years include pothole repair, repair after road collapse, electrical poles repair, as well as costs due to lawsuits by residents whose cars or basements were flooded.
- The municipality may be economically sensitive to increases in hot, dry weather due to **increased need for irrigation** of urban trees and plants.

Fig. 11 – Agricultural plots in Shefa-'Amr

Source: Ministry of Agriculture "Agricultural plots - public".

Sensitivity: recommendations

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include **a focus on neighborhoods/ statistical areas that have higher relative social vulnerability**. At the same time, **all neighborhoods** exhibit certain vulnerability factors, such as a relatively low socio-economic index, so measures should not only focus on those with the highest relative social vulnerability.
- Efforts to reduce exposure to climate hazards and increase adaptive capacity should include a focus on **physically and economically sensitive population groups**.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include **awareness raising** of heat-related health risks and ways to reduce exposure to heat, especially for sensitive population groups. Partners can include **local healthcare providers**.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should integrate existing and future **public health efforts** to prevent diabetes, heart disease and lung disease, in order to limit future physical sensitivity to heat.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan could include **support for local and/or urban agriculture**. For example, certain activities such as a local farmer’s market or community gardens can be ways to support the sector which can also contribute to other areas such as tourism, health, and community resilience. Farmers should be involved to define the support they may need. They could also work together to benefit from economies of scale.
- The municipality should **collect data by address** (street and street number) whenever possible to enable analysis and follow-up by neighborhood, statistical area (eg. for several national mapping initiatives) or planning units (for the engineering department and others working on implementation of the master plan).
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include a **strategic plan to reduce the need/cost for irrigation of urban vegetation**, using tools such as sustainable runoff management practices (e.g. water retention, containment and percolation – which could also contribute to lower risk of floods), the use of trees which require less water, and possibly the use of treated sewage water for irrigation (which might require infrastructure development).

Adaptive capacity

Adaptive capacity is the ability of systems, institutions and humans to adjust to potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to respond to consequences (adapted from UN IPCC 2021).

Financial capital

At the household level:

- **Shefa-‘Amr is in socio-economic index cluster 3 out of 10** (CBS 2019), indicating a relatively low socio-economic status.
- Based on 2008 and 2012 figures, statistical **areas 1 and 2** have relatively lower socio-economic status. However, the differences are **not large** – there is less variation between areas compared to several (mostly Jewish) localities of similar size.
- For some households, **access to energy for cooling and heating** represents a significant economic burden. However there is a lack of data from Shefa-‘Amr and other Arab localities to have a clear picture of how this actually impacts households and to what extent.

At the municipal level:

- The regular budget per capita has **increased every year** for the past decade, but the 2020 regular budget of Shefa-‘Amr is still **28.1% lower** than the national average.
- The municipality received budget for the elaboration of a local Climate Adaptation Plan via a government call for proposal, however there is no **specific budget, nor nationally nor locally, for the implementation** of such municipal plans.

Financial capital: recommendations

- The municipality should perform a **mapping of energy poverty/energy security to identify households at risk** and the types of support they need to ensure safe and stable cooling and heating; and define support policies accordingly.
- More stable and economically viable localities with **diversified income** are more resilient. The Injaz/Sikkuy-Aufoq 2022 report “Sources of income of Arab local authorities” provides relevant recommendations on this topic.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should highlight possible climate adaptation **measures that relate to income generation** (e.g. shade facilities with solar panels; developing sustainable tourism based on local economy; green building/ green renovation jobs) or **financial savings** (e.g. passive cooling).

Institutional capacity

- The **centralized structure of government** in Israel limits the authority and scope of influence of local authorities in several domains. This may create some barriers for municipalities who wish to develop and especially implement plans for climate change preparedness.
 - This is a greater challenge for communities who are **under-represented** in the centralized government and its institutions, including the Arab society.
 - These barriers might be more challenging considering the slow pace of planning and decision-making on climate change preparedness in many ministries.
- In Shefa-‘Amr, some of the **mechanisms designed to ensure good governance** such as municipal committees or the municipality comptroller have not been operating optimally in the past years. This may be a limiting factor for the design, implementation and monitoring of plans.
- **Public participation** in decision-making is considered key to good governance, in general as well as when minority groups are involved.
 - In Shefa-‘Amr, as in many localities in Israel, there is very little public participation, with a few notable exceptions: e.g. the youth council, the Muni100 ‘Optimal Ageing’ project, the community center’s volunteer group, and the public consultation meetings that were part of the Master Plan’s development process, and the Climate Resilience project (which this report is a part of, and in which the public participation is led by The Galilee Society together with the partners municipality and University of Haifa).
 - There used to be neighborhood committees. Re-initiating this is considered politically sensitive due to the delicate balance of interests in neighborhoods.
 - Issues such as the lack of trust in the municipality and the competition of interests between social groups make public participation challenging (see ‘social capital’).
- **Flood prevention is an example of challenges in institutional and financial capacity.**
 - Optimal flood prevention measures require coordination between different departments in the municipality and the regional drainage authorities, each of which have different priorities and level of knowledge and capacity. This coordination is based on goodwill as there is no formal coordinating mechanism or authority.
 - Neither of these authorities has sufficient budget dedicated to large flood prevention infrastructure investment. To overcome this, authorities typically leverage the budget for new development. However, this leaves areas that are already developed behind.

Institutional capacity: recommendations

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should highlight which measures can be implemented **independently** within the municipality’s authority and financial scope.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should highlight which measures require financial, policy or other support from external stakeholders. This can inform **relevant ministries and other stakeholders regarding the Shefa-‘Amr local authority needs** and priorities.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should assess options for long-term governance mechanism. This should involve a coordination mechanism as well as ownership and accountability within different departments (‘mainstreaming’).
- The process to develop (and update) the Climate Adaptation Plan, including the budget, should involve all relevant departments, the local council, as well as the mayor.
- Since a key driving mechanism of activity is the submission and implementation of proposals to **calls for proposal**, these should systematically consider the dimension of climate change preparedness.
- Using more strategic planning (e.g. 1 year, 5 years, longer-term) may help departments advocate for their budget needs more effectively.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should involve significant **public participation**, as well as measures to **enhance trust** between the municipality and the community.
 - This should involve public participation at planning stage, as well as in the implementation and monitoring stages.
 - The existing examples of public participation can provide insights on approaches that work well or less well.
 - Public participation should involve representation of different groups, including more vulnerable groups, as well as the different communities that live in Shefa-‘Amr.
 - This should involve the sharing of (updated) data, plans, budgets, as well as the details of meetings accessible to the public (e.g. committee meetings). This can be supported by accessible digitization of information.

Infrastructure and technology capacity

Health and social services

- Overall, there is a relatively **good availability of health and social services** in Shefa-‘Amr. There may be a lack of availability for specific population groups, such as people with disabilities.
- The number of residents without status or in the process of family reunification in Shefa-‘Amr is not known. Depending on their specific status, such residents may have significant barriers to accessing health services and no access to social security.

Electricity infrastructure and access

- Shefa-‘Amr has a **stable source of access to electricity** via the national grid. There are national risks of excessive load on the electricity network during times of peak demand, such as heat waves.
- Barriers to access are not related to infrastructure, but rather to poverty (see “energy poverty”) or to policy. In 2018 there were an estimated 165 buildings in Shefa-‘Amr without building permits (1-2% of buildings). These are presumably connected to the electricity via illegal connections which may be **unstable and/or unsafe**.
 - Housing regularization processes are ongoing via approvals of detailed plans, however this is expected to take a couple of years at best.

Surface runoff management and flood prevention infrastructure

- The municipality has taken and continues to take several measures for flood prevention, especially installing new/wider drainage pipes and cleaning gutters prior to the winter season. However, the full network of pipes described in the 2009 drainage master plan has not yet been implemented.
- None of the 4 **upstream regulation basins** described in the 2009 drainage master plans have been implemented. In one area, regulation terraces were built. In another area, a regulation basin will be built as part of development plan Tamal 1036.
 - Note that, depending on their location, regulation basins may involve the temporary flooding of agricultural fields. For example, agricultural land located south-east of the Somekh junction (within Kiryat Ata jurisdiction but owned by Shefa-'Amr residents) has been used as a regulation basin to prevent flooding in the Haifa bay. This is an example of a trade-off in climate change preparedness. In this case, the Kishon Drainage Authority financially compensates the farmers who are impacted by the regulation basins.
- There is a lack of application of surface runoff water management principles such as **retention, containment and percolation** in public and private spaces.
- A significant but unknown number of houses have **connected their rainwater gutters to the sewage system** in order to avoid large volumes of water spilling into their yards or neighboring yards. This increases the risk of sewage overflow during heavy rainfall events. The sanitary sewer system is not designed to accommodate rainwater in addition to sewage, since these connections are illegal. Rainwater from house gutters is part of surface runoff water, and should be dealt with via drainage and surface runoff water management.

Open public space infrastructure

- Despite the development of several football fields, playgrounds, and one small park in the past few years, there is still a **lack of public open space in Shefa-'Amr – especially neighborhood-level** public open spaces at a distance of 5 or 15 minute walk.
 - A key barrier is that areas designated as public open spaces in the master plan are currently still privately owned, and need to go through a process of expropriation for public use. This requires human resources capacity and can be politically sensitive. The lack of public open space and this particular barrier are specific to Arab localities in Israel.
 - Most open public spaces are sports fields, the majority being football fields which girls and women are less likely to use (although there are 4 girls football teams), and playgrounds for young children.
- **Overall walkability within the locality is low**, due to various factors such as lack of sidewalks, sidewalks with obstacles like holes or parked cars, lack of benches, lack of shade, lack of safety for pedestrians, etc.
 - Note that the 'Optimal Ageing' project's survey in Shefa-'Amr found that older adults do not walk enough, and that lack of shade was reported as one of the hazards by 71% of the survey respondents, along with other issues.

Other infrastructure and technology capacity topics that are relevant to climate adaptive capacity were beyond the scope of this assessment:

- **Public transport** - Weather may impact use if bus stops are not protected from the weather and/or a long walk away.
- **Irrigation water** - The water available for crops and public spaces irrigation in Shefa-'Amr is high quality drinking water, which is more expensive than treated wastewater commonly used in other areas.
- **Cellular reception** - Relevant to emergency response.
- **Digitization of municipal data and work processes** - Relevant to human resources capacity and making data available to the public.

Fig. 12 – Playgrounds and parks 250m range

Map created with ArcGIS Pro

Human capital

Municipality human capital

- **Government funding and legislation enabled the municipality to add several staff roles** in the past few years that are important to climate resilience, such as the Manager of Resource Utilization and Economic Development and a part-time urban planner (budgets from Government Resolution 922); 'Local Government Cadets' working on public spaces and economic development; the 3-year Muni100 Optimal Ageing project manager; the new Health Unit (budget from Government Resolution 550); and an additional staff member for the Municipal Comptroller department. However, there is no position with responsibility for climate change, sustainability department, landscape architect, nor hydrological engineer, all disciplines relevant to climate resilience.
- **External, contract-based consultants** are often hired to prepare plans (e.g. for calls for proposal), as well as for some part-time roles and multi-year projects. This may prevent the development of further professional knowledge within the municipality, and maybe also lower the potential of **implementation**.
- Several participants raised their concerns that **community relations** (e.g. family relations or being of a certain religion) have impacted the hiring of municipality employees, sometimes at the cost of professional competency.

General population education indicators

- Currently, the percentage of students eligible for a matriculation certificate among 12th grade students is **higher in Shefa-'Amr than the national average**.
- The percentage of academic degree holders ages 35-55 who obtained their degrees in Israel is lower than the national average, but it has been increasing.

Awareness and understanding of climate change

- According to our survey and focus groups, there is a **high awareness of climate change as a general concept** in the community and in the municipality, and people think it is a serious issue.
- At the same time, according to the focus groups there is a lack of deeper understanding of the phenomenon of climate change and its (local) effects.
- Prior to the Climate Resilience project, both the community and the municipality **associated the topic of climate change more with environmental issues** than with health, economic, or quality of life risks. As such they tend to associate climate-related action with mitigation topics (reduce greenhouse gas emissions) rather than with local preparedness.

Attitudes regarding preparedness and readiness to take adaptation measures

- According to the survey, there is a high willingness to act for preparedness actions like to sign a petition, learn more about climate change, plant trees, and adapt buildings to heat and to have appropriate drainage (83.8 – 89.8% willingness).
- On the other hand, there was less willingness to consider climate change and its impacts during elections, which signals other political priorities (65.6%). Perhaps this is in part due to people's association of climate-related action with mitigation rather than preparedness and resilience.
- In focus groups the community had a wide set of ideas to enhance climate resilience.

Open public space in the Released Soldiers [Veterans] new neighborhood A

'Ayn 'Afiye Road

Quotes 2 – Outdoor activity and public space in the context of heat

Decrease/different timing in outdoor activity during hot days

“All day we are at home, with the air conditioning on.”

“Basically, during hot days **no one goes outside the house.**”

Active transport/ walkability to reach daily destinations

“If my son wants to walk to school now [March 2022], I allow him. But in the summer no ... I drive them. ...in this current weather, the boy wants to walk, because it's a **10 minute walk**, so there's no problem, he wants to and I want him to, it's all good. But when it's hot, I don't want him to and he also doesn't want to.”

Spaces for leisure

“There are parks in Kiryat Ata with trees and places to sit, and walking paths, the swimming pool. **These are the minimum things that should be in every city.**”

“It is a basic right to have some public parks for us elderly people, so we could gather and chat maybe, **to communicate instead of feeling lonely at home.**”

““Even if they build parks here, I won't use them, I'll go elsewhere... have you seen the **garbage** in the streets?”

Infrastructure and technology capacity: recommendations

Health and social services infrastructure

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include **awareness of healthcare and social workers/ caregivers** regarding links between health and climate change.

Electricity

- The climate change preparedness plan should include **emergency planning** in case of (prolonged) electricity cuts focused on vulnerable population and critical sectors.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan cannot solve the issue of regularization of houses built without a permit. However, the plan can include **monitoring of the progress** on this issue, to promote stable and safe access to electricity.

Drainage and runoff water management

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should prioritize and include regular monitoring of the **implementation status of the drainage master plan** drainage pipes and regulation basins.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include a strategic plan to increase the awareness and use of **sustainable runoff water management principles** (retention, containment and percolation) in private and public areas.
 - Some of these can be applied relatively easily and quickly in places like parking lots of public institutions or roundabouts.
 - These should also be systematically included in submissions to call for proposals involving public open space (including roads).
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should also include a **partnership with the Water and Sewage Corporation** to raise awareness and find solutions regarding the issue of rainwater gutters connected to the sewage system.

Open public space

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should prioritize and include regular **monitoring of the development of plots designated as open public spaces** in the master outline plan.
 - There should be a focus on open public space **within neighborhoods** (5-15 minute walk) and that can serve the needs of **diverse groups** (different ages, different genders).
 - This includes prioritizing and monitoring the process of expropriation of spaces designated as public open spaces in the master plan, supported by a communication plan to address sensitive concerns.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include a strategic plan to **enhance walkability**, prioritizing areas around public services (schools, clinics, public transport, etc.), and connection between public open spaces.

Fig. 13 – Willingness to take adaptation actions, Shefa-'Amr survey 2021

Willingness to take adaptation actions

Residents survey 2021, 482 respondents

'Ayn 'Afiye park

Quotes 3 – Examples of community ideas for preparedness and resilience

“Shade. Not enough shade in houses, in the neighborhoods, at the seaside. Trees also help to absorb pollution, smell nice, and give a nice atmosphere to the neighborhood. People don’t know how important this is. The municipality leaders don’t know how important it is either.”

“First of all a tree, or two trees. And the **type of building.** .. for example insulation in walls, in roofs. For the balcony to be like this. Many people [currently] put a big window in the living room, maybe [instead] it should be smaller. Think about the orientation of the house, western or eastern.”

“This should be part of the social security [financial support to pay electricity bills], ... , because there are many children who find it hard to be in a hot environment, and they need air conditioning”

“Adjusting work hours, this really helps. Start earlier and fewer hours. And the productivity won’t be hurt. Also giving outdoor workers **good conditions,** for example contractors can arrange for some shade, and every two hours have a break.. instead of one break per day, there will be more.”

Human capital: recommendations

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should include a **training and resources plan for municipal staff** regarding topics relevant to each department, especially where there is an identified need (e.g. shade-promoting urban forestry, heat-adapted building, sustainable water runoff management, public participation, strategic planning, etc.). Some of these topics and related resources were included in the climate resilience project, but may require follow-up training, or the identification of updated resources to support staff (e.g. national guide on street shading).
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should **continue community awareness-raising** that started with the Climate Resilience project. This should include a focus on the local impacts and risks (which are not only environmental but also related to health, wellbeing and socioeconomics), as well as the possible positive impacts of climate adaptation on quality of life.
- Communication about climate adaptation may resonate more if it mentions **specific risks**, rather than the general term 'climate change'.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan can leverage the **high willingness** of people to take several preparedness actions.
- With regards to flood risk mapping, the Climate Adaptation Plan should **identify possible data gaps**. For example, mapping the existing drainage infrastructure is needed for a hydrological model to be developed.

Social capital

- Many focus group participants were part of existing **volunteer and social groups**, and most of these spoke very positively about such groups and social infrastructure such as the community centers, the senior centers, the scout movements, etc. However other participants indicated that there is not enough social infrastructure, or that they weren't aware of them.
- **Multi-generation households** enhance adaptive capacity for older adults living with family. However, the rate may be decreasing, although there is no quantitative data to confirm this.
 - Inter-generational support also goes the other way: older adults support their adult children in different ways.
- **Residents do not have a lot of confidence in the city's readiness regarding emergencies** and receiving aid from decision-makers in case of crisis. For example, the community resilience index from the survey was not high.
- There is severe mistrust between the community and the municipality, fueled by frustration regarding infrastructure and services, and concerns regarding corruption and the appointment of municipality employees based on relations.
 - At the same time, participants acknowledged the municipality's limited resources, and their own responsibilities such as in terms of public space cleanliness or attitudes towards municipal elections.
- The presence of **different communities** in Shefa-ʿAmr (such as Muslim, Christian, Druze, Bedouin) is a both a source of pride, in terms of a peaceful, diverse shared community, and an issue of concern, in terms of sectarianism and competing interests.

Quotes 4 - Mistrust in the municipality, call for the community to take responsibility, challenge of competing interests between groups and belonging

Focus group participants – mistrust, responsibility, competing interests, belonging

“There is vandalism, it’s true, but then there is no one who fixes the damage.”

“I try to say that we are part of the responsibility, not only to point one finger at you, but three fingers to myself. There are many good things in Shefa-'Amr. There is also a lot of corruption, in the institutions. It’s known, we all know it. [but you can take action and volunteer] The women are those who do, who volunteer.”

“We see that everything is deteriorating because there are no professionals in the municipality, there are no tenders.”

“We forget that we are the municipality – we elected them. But we elect according to who are our family, friends, religion.”

“There is a problem with belonging, connection and caring” –
Municipality employee

Fig. 14 – Social resilience, Shefa-'Amr survey 2021

Social capital: recommendations

- The Climate Adaptation Plan should consider how maintaining and further **strengthening social infrastructure** such as community centers, senior centers, youth centers, youth movements etc. contributes to social capital.
 - These organizations should consider how they can contribute to climate resilience.
 - Organizations that explicitly include inter-faith/inter-community audiences, initiatives and activities (even if this is not their main focus) may strengthen city-wide social capital.
 - Organizations should consider which members of their target population they might not be reaching, and develop strategies to be more accessible to these.
- Policies that enable households to remain **multi-generational** may contribute to lowering climate-related risks for older adults – e.g. policies related to housing, welfare or social security.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should consider policies and initiatives that can contribute to **building trust between the community and the municipality**.
 - Areas of attention may include transparency, responsiveness (e.g. via the call center), public participation, and joint initiatives.

Playground in Al-Fawar neighborhood

Natural/environmental capital

This report did not assess natural/environmental capital, but it is a relevant part of adaptive capacity.

Natural/environmental capital: recommendations

The Climate Adaptation Plan should consider resources such as the forest areas, natural springs, wadi streams, flora, fauna and the ecosystem services they provide. These resources can contribute to developing and implementing nature-based solutions.

Pedestrian needs pyramid

Source: Alfonzo, 2005 in התוכנית הלאומית להליכה במרחב העירוני

Streets network: one of the contributors to walkability

Low junctions density

High junctions density

“A good streets network for pedestrians provides them with **many options and shortcuts to reach their destination**. The higher the **number of junctions**, the more complex the walking network, providing more walking routes.”

Source: מראה מקום

Barriers to frequently leaving the house (ages 55+)

Number of respondents: 312
 Source: Optimal Ageing survey Shefa-'Amr, 2023

Physical accessibility - hazards in the urban environment (ages 55+)

Number of respondents: 312
 Source: Optimal Ageing survey Shefa-'Amr, 2023

Conclusion

- **Shefa-'Amr today is not adapted to the current climate, and there are already existing impacts of extreme heat and rainfall.** The large dependence on air conditioning has financial and environmental costs, and is a risk in case of electricity cuts. There is a lack of shade in public spaces such as sidewalks, bus stops and sports fields. Rainwater-related floods and sewage overflow cause damage every year. In conclusion, the issue is not only preparing for future climate change, but also improving adaptation to the current climate. This also means that the benefits of many climate adaptation measures will be felt quickly in terms of quality of life, and not only in the long-term, which is a good incentive to start taking action now.
- **In several cases climate change is a 'threat multiplier', as hazards exacerbate existing issues.**
 - Some of these existing issues are: the lack of walkability and public transport, the lack of open public spaces (especially within walking distance and serving different ages and genders), the poor state of existing open public spaces, or public safety. In all of these cases, rising temperatures may further reduce the ability to use public space.
 - Limited ability to use public space may also be a barrier to physical activity, which is required to prevent or manage prevalent (heat-sensitive) health conditions, such as diabetes or cardiovascular conditions.
 - Another example is people who grow olives as part of tradition, and the few people who continue to make a living from crops or livestock – for them, extreme weather also adds to other pressures (e.g. residential development plans, cost of fuel).
- **Co-benefits:** since climate-related risks are related to existing issues, many climate adaptation measures can help to address existing economic, social and environmental issues as well. For example, increasing tree cover not only provides shade, but also contributes to **cleaner air**. Similarly, increasing walkability makes it easier to be active also on hot days, and may also reduce the number of cars and related issues like air pollution, **traffic jams** and parking space demands. As a different example, shade for sports fields may be topped by solar panels, which can provide **income** or electricity savings.
- Conversely, there are initiatives that primarily target other issues, but can **also contribute to climate change preparedness**. For example, the Russel Berrie Galilee SPHERE diabetes initiative is entirely focused on diabetes prevention and management. Since diabetes increases physical sensitivity to heat, this initiative contributes to climate change adaptation.
- **There may also be cases of trade-offs.** For example, upstream regulation basins to prevent urban flooding may require temporary flooding of agricultural lands. These may require compromise or specific measures, such as compensating farmers in case of damage in this example.
- Some issues require **close cooperation between the community and the municipality**. For example, the development of public space within the densely built environment, with most of the land being private.
 - Mistrust between the community and the municipality as well as competing interests may hinder the ability to develop and implement solutions for such issues.
 - **Building trust between the municipality and the community**, as well as within the different communities may help address such issues.

- While there are limitations to the municipality’s institutional and financial capacity to address risks alone, Shefa-‘Amr has many resources that it can build on and strengthen for climate resilience. For example:
 - Numerous health, social and educational facilities
 - Numerous active religious institutions
 - An active civil society and significant community willingness to take action (note point above regarding trust)
 - The high percentage of older adults living in multi-generational households
 - The existing appreciation of trees
 - Direct personal interest of individuals to build climate-adapted, comfortable and energy-efficient private homes
 - Old City neighborhoods’ good starting point regarding walkability with dense network of small streets and destinations
 - Pride in the diversity of the Shefa-‘Amr community
 - The connection of many climate adaptation measures with traditional local and regional knowledge and practices (see box below)

Connecting climate adaptation with heritage and local knowledge

Many climate adaptation measures have a connection with traditional local and regional knowledge and practices. Adaptation to climate may be an opportunity to celebrate heritage and build further on it in the modern context. Examples include:

Within municipality scope

- Climate-adapted walkability in the dense, historical Old City neighborhoods
- Connection with land via nature (e.g. natural springs ‘Ayn ‘Afiye and Al-Fawar)
- Transitioning to sustainable runoff water management is aligned with the traditional view of rain as a blessing, rather than a hazard

Within municipality and private scope

- Using local, climate-adapted varieties of trees for shade, preserving older trees
- Public drinking fountains
- ‘Hawakir’ (orchard garden as part of traditional homes), possibly in a modern, urban application such as a ‘public hakura community garden’

Within private scope

- Multi-generational households
- Climate-adapted traditional architecture
- Connection with land via crops and livestock (e.g. olive groves, which contribute to green space within the built environment)
- Climate-adapted traditional clothing

Fig. 15 – Examples of traditional elements adapted to heat

Examples of traditional house and street-level elements adapted to heat in modern-day Shefa-'Amr: grapevine pergolas, 'sabeel' water fountains, small windows, building envelope using traditional design (similar to 'mashrabiye')

Conclusion: recommendations

- In addition to long-term measures, the climate preparedness plan should include “**low-hanging fruit**” measures that address existing climate-related risks, can be applied in the short-term and also enhance quality of life and wellbeing in the short-term.
- For climate adaptation measures to be most effective, they should consider the wider context and associated issues. The Climate Adaptation Plan should take a **holistic view on issues such as public open space, walkability, public transport, public health etc.**
 - For example, if the goal is to make public spaces more usable during hot days, the focus of adaptation proposals should not be only on adaptation to heat, but also include other factors that are required for usability such as cleanliness, safety and serving a diverse range of people including girls, women and older adults.
 - One way to achieve this is to clearly **connect the Climate Adaptation Plan with other strategic plans** that address issues like public space (including safety and cleanliness), walkability, public transport, or public health.
- The climate preparedness plan should **identify possible co-benefits**, to highlight possible additional health, economic, social and environmental benefits of climate adaptation measures. The plan should also identify **possible trade-offs**.
- Departments with **initiatives that do not primarily target climate adaptation** should consider whether their initiatives do include some contributions to climate adaptation.
- The Climate Adaptation Plan should **build on existing characteristics and resources**.

Thank you to all the focus group participants and interviewees

*Not all focus groups were photographed

Selected references

For full list, see the full report on The [Galilee Society](#) website.

Project databases

47 different publicly available indicators/datasets were used as part of this assessment. These were consolidated into two databases available in Hebrew:

- מקורות נתונים להכנת הערכת פגיעות לשינוי אקלים ברשויות מקומיות
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Adaptive capacity – infrastructure, public space

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3. [Flooded street](#), Facebook page “اخبارنا الآن”
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11. [Flooded yard](#), Facebook post
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16. [Flooded house/building](#), Facebook page “הנה שפאערו والمنطقة”

Appendix – list of interviewees and reviewers

Name	Role
Omar Malek	Municipality, CEO
Itamar Siegelmann	Municipality 'cadet', CEO Assistant (former)
Jeris Hana	Municipality, Deputy/Acting Mayor (former)
Farid Shaheen	Municipality, Head of Welfare
Avi Tayer*	Municipality, Head of 'Shefa' department ⁴
Yasser Hassan*	Municipality 'cadet', Project manager 'Shefa' department, incl. for the Climate Adaptation Plan project
Maha Hamudi	Municipality, Deputy Head Engineering
Maria Nakhtiger	Municipality, Strategic Consultant Engineering Department
Farid Hasun*	Municipality, Infrastructure Manager
Karem Sobeh	Municipality, Head of Sports
Safaa Hamada Taha*	Municipality, Head of 'Optimal Aging' Project (former)
Hani Jarjura*	Municipality, Resource Utilization
Hind Khatib	Municipality 'cadet', Economic & Strategic Development
Badia Khanifes	Municipality, Advisor Advancement of Women
Wasseem Haj	Municipality, Head of Early Childhood Center
Dr. Abid Elkarim Amsha*	Municipality, Head of the Public Health Department
Sara Hosary*	Municipality, Health Coordinator
Elham Abu Elardat	Municipality, Assets Department Lawyer
Essam Nassralla	Municipality, Comptroller
Wasseem Magarba	Municipality, Deputy comptroller

Name	Role
Maysa Shaban Haj Ali	Community Center, Head of Community Department
Ali Ayub	Resident, Head of Muslim Scouts Shefa-'Amr and Chairman of Arab Peace Scouts Organization
Raja Saad	Resident, Former Head of Agricultural Committee
Elay Koren	Hamifrats Regional Cluster, Director of Sustainability (former)
Brook Totari	Hamifrats Regional Cluster, Local government 'cadet'
Firas Kababu	Meyah Water Corporation, Head of Operations
Tareq Haj	Meyah Water Corporation, Head of Engineering
Haim Hemi	Kishon Drainage Authority, Head
Uri Regev*	Kishon Drainage Authority, Head of Engineering Department
Ayman Asad	Givat Alonim Local Planning Committee, Head of Planning Department
Eyad Khanifes	Givat Alonim Local Planning Committee, Head of Inspection Department
Sudki Dexa	Netivi Ayalon, Traffic Engineer
Amit Koltin	Palgey Maim, Drainage engineer
German Rudnik*	National Center for Flood Forecasting, Urban Flood Coordinator
Prof. Itay Beeri	University of Haifa, Professor Local Government
Prof. Rassem Khamaisi	University of Haifa, Professor Urban and Regional Planning
Prof. Naomi Carmon	Technion, Professor Emerita, Urban Planning and Sociology
Prof. David Broday*	Technion, Professor Civil and Environmental Engineering
Dr. Rakefet Shafan-Nathan*	Taub Center Research and Policy Initiative for Environment and Health, Senior Researcher

*These stakeholders also reviewed drafts of different sections of the full report related to their area of responsibility. Additional reviewers: Dr. Gideon Toperoff (Ministry of Agriculture, Chief Professional Instructor of Sustainable Agriculture and Climate Change Preparedness), Manar Sarie Weiss (Community Coordinator, The Galilee Society).

⁴ 'Shefa' department has multiple responsibilities related to the public space: waste collection and disposal, veterinary services, pest control, licensing of businesses, landscaping, development and maintenance of public spaces. The Shefa department is currently leading the municipality's Climate Adaptation Plan development process, financed and guided by the Ministry of Environment.

'Ayn 'Afiye Road

